

Polymerization of acrylamide initiated by $K_2S_2O_8$ -EDTA- Ag^+ redox system

A. K. Bajpai*, J. Bajpai and R. Dengre

Bose Memorial Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Government Autonomous Science College, Jabalpur-482 001, India

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Kinetics of the polymerization of acrylamide have been studied employing $K_2S_2O_8$ -EDTA- Ag^+ redox couple under atmospheric oxygen. The rate expression has been obtained and a plausible mechanism suggested. The effects of varying concentrations of monomer, redox components, temperature, added salts, H^+ ions and surfactants on the polymerization kinetics have been studied.

Polyacrylamide have been synthesized using a variety of redox systems¹. Among them the persulfate initiated systems are unique place because of their simplicity and efficiency. The persulfate either alone or with some suitable redox component has been investigated in the recent past². Although a variety of compounds have been coupled with the persulfate, however, the use of chelating agents in polymerizing vinyl monomers has not been studied adequately³. In the present investigation, a three-component system comprising of $K_2S_2O_8$ -EDTA- Ag^+ has been employed for the polymerization of acrylamide.

Results and Discussion

A stepwise plausible mechanism for the polymerization of acrylamide by the persulfate-EDTA-redox couple may be outlined as below.

(a) Formation of free radicals :

and $X = CH_2CO_2H$

(b) Initiation :

(c) Propagation :

(d) Termination :

In addition to the above bimolecular termination, unimolecular termination can also take place following any of the suggested mechanisms.

(i) By electron transfer :

In this type of termination, the growing macroradical transfers its electrons to the metal ion⁴.

(ii) By dissolved impurity :

Dissolved metal ion impurity may also cause termination of growing macroradicals,

Based on the above mechanism and applying steady state assumptions, the following rate expression is derived,

$$R_p = 2k_i(k_p/k_t)^{1/2} [M] [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1/2} / \{ [Ag^+]^{1/2} + (k)^{1/2} [EDTA]^{1/2} \} \quad (10)$$

This rate expression is able to explain the experimental findings.

Initiator effect : The effect of persulfate on the kinetics of polymerization has been studied by varying its concentration in the range 2.0×10^{-2} to 8.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} . The results (Fig. 1) imply that both initial rate and limiting conversion increases with the increasing concentration of initiator. The increase may be due to the fact that with the increasing $[K_2S_2O_8]$ a greater number of free radicals are generated (Eqns. 1 and 4) and as a result the initial rate and percent conversion are increased.

Fig. 1. Time vs conversion curve for the polymerization of acrylamide with varying initial persulfate concentration (mol dm^{-3}); $[\text{Monomer}] = 10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ag}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{EDTA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{temp.} = 28 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

From the double logarithmic plot, the exponent with respect to the initiator was found to be 0.73 which is greater than the expected 0.5 order. The half-order dependence normally confirms the bimolecular terminated polymerization mechanism. However, a value between 0.5 and unity implies a mixed termination, i.e. a bimolecular and a metal ion caused unimolecular termination, as reported earlier⁵.

Catalyst effect : On raising the concentration of $AgNO_3$ from 0.30×10^{-3} to $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the initial rate of polymerization increases. At higher concentrations (1.2×10^{-3} to $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) the initial rate is increased but the limiting conversion decreases remarkably. The increase in initial rate may be due to the formation of larger number of initiating free radicals. From the double logarithmic plot the order was found to be 0.48 which is a widely reported result⁶.

Monomer effect : The effect of variation of the initial monomer concentration (0.8×10^{-2} to $10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) results in an increase in the initial rate as well as percent conversion. The increase in rate may be due to the availability of larger number of monomer molecules in propagation step. However, at higher concentration ($>12.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) the percent conversion falls due to the fact that the growing macroradicals undergo rapid termination by primary radicals.

From the double logarithmic plot, the order with respect to monomer has been calculated to be 1.0. It has also been found that at higher monomer concentration the order decreases to 0.3. The change in order with respect to monomer can be attributed to the presence of impurity and high percent conversion⁷.

Activator [EDTA] effect : The effect of EDTA has been studied by varying the concentration of EDTA in the range 0.5 to $8.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ where an increase in the initial rate and limiting conversion is observed, while beyond $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ the initial rate and the percent conversion decrease. The increase observed in the initial rate and limiting conversion may be attributed to the fact that with increasing concentrations of EDTA, greater number of initiating free radicals are produced and the initial rate and limiting conversion will increase. However, upon increasing the concentration of EDTA beyond $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the fall in the initial rate and percent conversion is due to the reason that at higher concentration of EDTA the complex formed between the Ag^+ and EDTA may not be so unstable to dissociate to give the free radicals (EDTA). The order with respect to EDTA was found to be 0.45 which is in accordance with the mechanistic predictions.

Surfactant effect : The effect of anionic surfactant on the course of polymerization has been investigated by adding sodium oleate to the reaction medium at below and above CMC value. The results indicate a fall in the initial rate and percent conversion which may be explained by the fact that due to the binding of Ag^+ ions to the anionic end of surfactant, the rate of generation of initiating free radicals decreases, resulting in a decrease in initial rate and percent conversion. Similar type of result has also been reported earlier⁸.

In case of addition of cationic surfactant (CTAB) the colour of reaction solution turns brown and finally a precipitate was observed. Hence, the effect of cationic surfactant could not be studied. Friend and Alexander⁹ also observed the formation of an insoluble complex between cationic surfactant and $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ions above CMC.

Temperature effect : The effect of temperature on the kinetics of polymerization was investigated by varying the temperature of medium in the range 13 – 50° . It was found that a rise in the temperature of the solution causes increase in initial polymerization rate and percent conversion because of the reason that at higher temperature the rate of active centre formation also increases which, as a consequence, enhances the rate of polymerization. The fall in the limiting conversion at 40 and 50° may be due to the initiation of some side-reactions. Similar type of results was also reported earlier¹⁰. The energy of activation as calculated from Arrhenius plot was found to be $12.04 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

pH effect : In the present case the effect of pH was studied by varying it in the range 4.6 – 11.0 by the addition of $0.1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and 0.1 M NaOH to the reaction mixture. The results reveal that at pH 4.6 initial rate and percent conversion become maximum at pH 4.6. The reason for the

observed maximum initial rate may be that the added H^+ ions combine with persulfate ions to give sulfate ion radicals¹¹,

This obviously brings about an increase in the initial rate and maximum percentage conversion. However, with decreasing H^+ ion concentration in the system the above reaction takes place to a lesser extent thus producing a lower number of free radicals. This obviously results in decrease in initial rate and percent conversion.

Effect of added inorganic salts : The effect of cations and anions on the kinetics of polymerization was studied by adding equimolar (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) concentrations of inorganic salts to the reaction medium. In order to study the anionic effect, salts of sodium were added to the medium. The results indicate that initial rate and limiting conversion decrease in order : $NO_3^- < SO_4^{2-} < PO_4^{3-}$. The reason may be given as follows : (i) The added anions cause a change in the ionic strength of the medium resulting in a change in the initial rate and limiting conversion. (ii) The added anions may also cause a screening of coulombic forces between reacting ions in the system that may also change the initial rate and limiting conversion. It is also clear from the observed order of effectiveness of the added ions that the extent of screening will increase with the increasing valency of the added anions and thus the order of effectiveness is justified.

The influence of addition of cation on the initial rate and limiting conversion has been investigated by adding halides of alkali metal ions (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) to the polymerization system. The results reveal that the added cations brings about a depression in the initial rate and limiting conversion and the increasing order of depression follows the sequence, $Li^+ < Na^+ < K^+$.

Conclusions : In the redox polymerization of acrylamide initiated by $K_2S_2O_8$ and catalyzed by silver ions, the presence of chelating agents like EDTA makes the system much more efficient. The rate of polymerization

varies with the first power to the monomer and half power to the three components comprising of the redox system. The termination of growing macroradicals takes place via mixed termination, i.e. both bimolecular and unimolecular. The rate of polymerization is significantly affected by the presence of inorganic salts and surfactants, pH and temperature.

Experimental

Acrylamide (E. Merck) was recrystallized from methanol (G.R.) and dried under reduced pressure over anhyd. silica gel for a week. Potassium persulfate (Loba Chemie) was used as received. Silver nitrate (B.D.H.) was used as such. All the solutions used were prepared in double-distilled water.

The apparatus, the polymerization technique and the formula for calculating the percentage conversion were described earlier¹².

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